

THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON ASYLUM SEEKERS IN THE AUTONOMOUS PROVINCE OF BOLZANO, ITALY

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1. INTRODUCTION

The outbreak of COVID-19 in early 2020 triggered a series of unprecedented regulatory and administrative actions by the Italian government, as well as regional and local authorities, aiming to mitigate the pandemic's impact on public health and safety. This report provides an analysis of measures undertaken to regulate international protection applications and the accommodation of asylum seekers during the first six months of the COVID-19 pandemic. Key legislative actions, such as Decree-Law No. 9/2020 and Decree-Law No. 18/2020, are examined to understand their impact on the legal status and living conditions of asylum seekers. It also explores the specific measures taken in the Province of Bolzano and the Municipality of Bolzano, highlighting local adaptations and responses.

Asylum seekers in Italy can be considered a vulnerable minority during the COVID-19 pandemic due to several compounding factors that exacerbated their precarious situation. Many asylum seekers lived in crowded reception centers or informal settlements, where social distancing and proper sanitation were challenging to maintain, heightening their risk of infection. Additionally, they often faced barriers to accessing healthcare, including language obstacles, lack of information, and discrimination. Furthermore, the legal and bureaucratic processes for asylum applications were delayed, prolonging their uncertainty and stress. These intertwined challenges underscored the heightened vulnerability of asylum seekers in Italy during the COVID-19 crisis. In 2020, Italy received 26.963 requests for international protection, way less than in the precedent years (Ufficio centrale di statistica, 2022).

2. THE COVID-19 RESPONSE - LEGAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. OVERVIEW GENERAL RESPONSE

The outbreak of COVID-19 prompted a significant number of regulatory and administrative actions from the Italian government, parliament, as well as regional and local authorities within their respective jurisdictions. The government's response followed two distinct but complementary paths: the Civil Protection Code and special "emergency" decree-laws. Both approaches were based on specific primary legislative acts, driven by the imperative to protect human life and health.

The initial response was the declaration of a nationwide state of emergency (Gazzetta Ufficiale, 2020) on 31 January 2020. This decree, issued by the Council of Ministers and signed by its president Giuseppe Conte, followed the identification of the first positive cases in Italy and the World Health Organization's (WHO) declaration of a Public Health Emergency of International Concern the previous day. The decree was grounded in the Civil Protection Code, established by Legislative Decree No. 1 of 2 January 2018. The activation of the Civil Protection Code resulted in various subsequent ordinances from the Head of the Civil Protection Department, the Extraordinary Commissioner for the Emergency, and decrees and circulars from the Minister of Health and other ministers, as well as prefectural ordinances on civil protection.

It is important to note that the Civil Protection Code does not explicitly empower the government to limit fundamental rights and freedoms (Alber, 2020). The only provision allowing such limitations is Article 78 of the Italian Constitution. With prior authorization from Parliament, this article grants the Government the authority to suspend fundamental rights and freedoms in the event of a state of war. Such suspensions are implemented through governmental decrees that hold the same legal force as laws. These governmental decrees are also envisaged by Article 77 of the Constitution, which permits their use in cases of necessity and urgency.

The issuance of governmental decrees, a too frequent and often criticized practice in Italy, led to decree-laws and conversion laws, as well as administrative decrees and directives from the President of the Council of Ministers (DPCM). With the declaration of the state of emergency, there was a centralization of power, both horizontally from the legislative to the executive branch and vertically from regional to national levels (Alber and Zgaga, 2021).

Decree 19/2020, enacted on 25 March 25 2020, stipulated that the presidents of the regions and autonomous provinces, as well as mayors, could implement additional, temporary, and more restrictive measures in response to particular health emergencies within their areas.

The measures taken to counter COVID-19 have impacted all sectors of public life, including health, education, transportation, cultural and sports activities, and economic activities, among others. Several provisions had significant implications for foreign nationals. With specific regard to asylum seekers in the initial phase of the COVID-19 pandemic Italy focused on prolonging their stay in accommodations, extending legal protections, and implementing strict health protocols within reception facilities.

2.2. INTERNATIONAL PROTECTION APPLICATIONS

The aim of this report is to provide guidance for a better understanding of the numerous provisions concerning the status of international protection applications during the first six months of the COVID-19 pandemic. To this end, the focus is particularly on Decree-Law (DL) No. 9/2020 of 2 March 2020, and Decree-Law No. 18/2020 of 17 March 17 2020.

Article 9 of DL 9/2020 established that the proceedings of the Public Security Authority, including those related to the residence permits of foreign nationals, were suspended for 30 days starting 2 March 2020. This suspension also applied to applications for the issuance or renewal of residence permits or declarations of presence (for those entering exempt from visa requirements). Consequently, until 31 March 2020, foreign nationals did not incur any penalties (such as deportation or fines) for not applying for a residence permit (issuance or renewal) within the legal deadlines, as these deadlines were suspended.

Furthermore, on 9 March 2020, the Ministry of the Interior ordered the closure of the immigration offices at police headquarters (Circular 0020359). No specific reopening date was provided, but associations interpreted this closure as lasting until 31 March 2020 (Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione (ASGI) Emilia Romagna, 2020). Immigration offices remained open for the reception of applications for international protection and for expulsions. Appointments for international protection applications could be made via certified post or by visiting the immigration office directly. In summary it

can be said that until the end of March 2020, it was not possible to apply for the issuance or renewal of residence permits, but this did not result in any sanctions for foreign nationals.

Article 103 of DL 18/2020, published on 17 March 2020, stated that residence permits expiring between 31 January and 15 April 2020, would remain valid until 15 June 2020. Additionally, Article 104 of the same decree law stipulated that recognition and identity documents (pursuant to Article 1, paragraph 1, letters c) and d) of Presidential Decree No. 445/2000) expiring from 17 March 2020, would remain valid until 31 August 2020.

The following scenarios applied to residence permits:

- Residence permit expired before 31 January 2020: If the residence permit expired before that date, and the application for renewal had been submitted by then, it remained valid until 15 April 2020. This due to the suspension of deadlines related to administrative procedures until 15 April 2020, as per Article 103, paragraph 1 of DL 18/2020.
- Residence permit expires between 31 January 2020 and 15 April 2020: According to Article 103(2) of DL 18/2020, the residence permit remained valid until 15 June 2020.
- Residence permit expired after 17 March 2020: Article 104 of DL 18/2020 stated that identification cards expiring that date, retained their validity until 31 August 2020. Given that residence permits could be equated with identification cards, it could be assumed that residence permits expiring after 17 March 2020, remain valid until 31 August 2020.

The suspension of hearings before commissions and territorial sections for the recognition of the right to asylum was also extended until 13 April 2020, following Order No. 2893 of 2 April 2020, from the National Commission for the Right to Asylum. This decision aligned with the Prime Minister's Decree of 1 April 2020, which extended the containment measures to counter the COVID-19 infection until 13 April 2020.

The decree also suspended public counter activities at each commission, while office activities continued in a hybrid work mode. Hearings with asylum seekers had already been suspended in response to government measures for the health emergency. Initially, the suspension applied only to the commissions and territorial sections in the so-called red zones (Order No. 1788 of 24 February 24 2020, from the National Commission), but it was later extended to all commissions nationwide (Order No. 2327 of 10 March 2020), and subsequently extended until 13 April 13 2020. The primary aim was to minimize the movement of people and documents and reduce gatherings as much as possible.

2.3. ASYLUM SEEKERS ACCOMMODATION

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Italian government took special measures concerning asylum seekers accommodations. The overarching goal was to mitigate the risk of virus transmission within migrant and refugee populations while ensuring the continuity of essential services and legal protections.

One of the initial steps was to maintain the accommodation of asylum seekers in the existing reception facilities, such as primary and secondary reception centers and CAS (Extraordinary Reception Centers),

even if the legal conditions for their stay had expired. This directive was included in the "Cura Italia" law (Law No. 27/2020), specifically in Article 86. The measure also applied to unaccompanied foreign minors, who were allowed to remain in reception centers beyond reaching adulthood.

To prevent COVID-19 outbreaks within these facilities, the government implemented strict health monitoring protocols. These included continuous health checks to identify COVID-19 symptoms early, provision of hygiene materials, and ensuring rigorous cleanliness of living and service areas. Additionally, new arrivals had to undergo preliminary medical examinations and a mandatory 14-day quarantine in separate accommodations to prevent potential spread within the centers. This was in accordance with directives issued by the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of the Interior, namely Circular of 5 March 2020, n. 5587, Circular of 18 March 2020, n. 3393 and Circular of 1 April 2020, n. 3728.

The three latter mentioned documents provide detailed guidelines and protocols concerning the accommodation and handling of asylum seekers and other foreigners in light of the COVID-19 pandemic. The documents collectively establish a comprehensive framework to manage the accommodation of asylum seekers and other foreigners during the pandemic, prioritizing health screenings, quarantine measures, hygiene practices, and clear communication to prevent the spread of COVID-19.

The government also allowed the use of SIPROIMI structures, which were typically reserved for refugees and unaccompanied minors, to house those under quarantine or isolation orders. This measure, outlined in the Decree Law No. 18/2020, aimed to effectively isolate symptomatic individuals or those exposed to the virus.

3. PROVINCIAL AND MUNICIPAL MEASURES IMPACTING ON ASYLUM SEEKERS

3.1. INTERNATIONAL PROTECTION APPLICATIONS

Being the asylum request regulated by national law, the Autonomous Province of Bolzano had no competence of legal interventions. The Immigration office of Bolzano was indeed closed until 3 April, 2020 (Questura di Bolzano, 2020), as ordered by the Ministry of Interior (see section 2.2.). The final hearings of the asylum requests are processed by the Territorial Commission of Verona, that followed the closings suggested by the Italian government.

3.2. ASYLUM SEEKERS ACCOMMODATION

During the first six months of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, the Province of Bolzano and the Municipality of Bolzano implemented a series of measures to manage the accommodation and support of asylum seekers, ensuring their health and safety amidst the crisis. These measures were guided by both national directives and local initiatives.

On 12 March 2020 the Province of Bolzano issued *Raccomandazioni generali per i Servizi Sociali residenziali* (General Recommendations for residential social services), with validity until 3 April 2020. Those initial recommendations aimed at residential facilities, including those for asylum seekers and the homeless. The primary focus was on enhancing hygiene practices and ensuring compliance with COVID-19 containment measures. Key recommendations included the intensification of standard hygiene practices to protect both residents and staff. This included the use of surgical masks, maintaining a social distance of at least 1 meter, and ensuring frequent hand washing and disinfection. The strict adherence to emergency measures outlined in the Decree of the President of the Council of Ministers dated 9 March 2020, and Law Decree No. 14 of 9 March 2020, which focused on COVID-19 containment and emergency management, were also mentioned in the document. This included regular health monitoring of residents, with special attention to vulnerable groups such as individuals with disabilities, mental illnesses, and addiction issues. These recommendations aimed to minimize the risk of COVID-19 transmission within residential facilities and ensure the safety of both the residents and the staff.

Raccomandazioni integrative alle strutture residenziali per persone con disabilità, con una malattia psichica e dipendenza patologica, per le donne, i minori, per l'IPAI, per i servizi per profughi, servizi a bassa soglia per i senza fissa dimora, il servizio di aiuto domiciliare, il servizio pasti a domicilio, i distretti sociali in relazione al COVID-19 issued by the Province on 15 April 2020 provided additional guidelines to supplement the measures in Allegato 1, extending their validity until 3 May 2020. It considered asylum seekers, unless elderly or with underlying health conditions, not in the highest risk group for COVID-19. Nevertheless, high attention to hygiene and compliance with hygiene rules by both operators and guests were considered mandatory, including frequent hand washing. Recommendations mentioned that all facilities and services had to undergo extraordinary disinfection by a specialized company and thorough weekly cleaning by a cleaning company. Guests' clothes had to be washed at 60°C. Surgical masks should be used by guests with cold and cough symptoms. If a guest had a fever above 37.5°C and isolation was not possible, the General Practitioner must be notified for further instructions. Guests leaving the accommodation centers could be readmitted following national regulations but had to be monitored if they showed flu symptoms and a fever above 37.5°C. Visits remained prohibited, with exceptions. No visitor showing flu-like symptoms was allowed. Facility operators must maintain personal hygiene and responsible behavior outside of work. Young, healthy volunteers could work in these facilities if properly trained. Users should be repeatedly reminded to intensify personal hygiene and comply with national movement restrictions. The recommendations reference also the Ministry of Interior circular dated 1 April 1 2020, and the document "Guidelines for Preventing the Spread of COVID-19 in Public Catering" from the Prevention Department of the South Tyrol Health Authority.

On 19 May 2020 the Province of Bolzano approved the *Provincial plan for the reactivation phase of the Territorial Social Services and for the return to regime of residential social services in different sectors* approved by Deliberation No. 352/2020. It outlined a strategic approach for reactivating social services and returning to regular operations. However, concerning asylum seekers accommodations the plan stated that measures described in the previously mentioned recommendation of 12 March and 15 April 2020 remained in effect until the end of the of emergency caused by COVID-19.

On a more local level, the Municipality of Bolzano implemented a range of measures to support homeless individuals and asylum seekers. In 2020 it collaborated with various associations to provide essential services such as medication delivery, grocery shopping, school materials printing, and psychological support. They distributed food vouchers worth 568.900 Euros to 1.545 families facing economic

difficulties. Additionally, they temporarily activated 30 extra beds for the homeless at the *Palasport* in Resia street, later moving to the *Fiera di Bolzano*, which provided shelter for approximately 120 individuals (Brentari and Recla, 2021).

4. PERCEPTIONS FROM THE FIELD

4.1. CHALLENGES FOR INTERNATIONAL PROTECTIONS REQUESTS

In March 2020, the Association for Legal Studies on Immigration (*Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione* – ASGI) issued a report, claiming that while it was possible to access the Police Headquarters to apply for international protection, there was not always a guarantee of effective presence in the relevant offices. This meant that booking an appointment to formalize an asylum application was not always possible. Consequently, many foreign nationals were at risk of being stopped by the police without valid documentation for their movement and residence, leading to serious legal repercussions (Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione, 2020).

In the same report, ASGI claimed for an amendment extending the validity of all residence permits and travel documents for 6 months to a year, with potential further extensions as needed. It was also requested that foreign nationals be allowed to request appointments for international protection, or first issuance of residence permits via certified email (PEC) to avoid physical gatherings at Immigration Offices. Finally, there was a call for the suspension of notifications of decisions by territorial commissions for international protection during the emergency period.

The suspension of administrative services for regulating immigration status affected asylum seekers' ability to regularize their legal status and access public benefits. Delays in immigration procedures and uncertainties about their future in the country added to the challenges faced by asylum seekers. This uncertainty about the future, social isolation, and disruptions in social services and support systems during the lockdown contributed to psychological distress among asylum seekers. Feelings of anxiety, frustration, and powerlessness were reported, highlighting the mental health challenges faced by this vulnerable group (Sanfelici, 2021).

4.2. CHALLENGES IN ASYLUM SEEKERS ACCOMMODATION SYSTEMS

The ASGI report highlighted several critical issues regarding the accommodation of foreign nationals during the COVID-19 crisis. It underscored how the overcrowded conditions in large collective centers, made it impossible to adhere to legal hygiene measures like maintaining a one-meter distance, frequent hand washing, and preventing gatherings, thereby posing a severe risk to public health.

The implementation of new management protocols in place since 2018 had resulted in a significant reduction of healthcare personnel, severely limiting medical support with minimal availability in facilities housing up to 300 people. This inadequate healthcare access for residents, especially during a pandemic, highlighted the urgent need for reform. Additionally, the precarious living conditions for many foreign

nationals, including the homeless and those in informal settlements, further exacerbated their vulnerability to COVID-19 due to poor sanitation and lack of basic amenities.

Considering these issues, the report urgently requested the closure of large collective centers in favor of a decentralized accommodation system that would ensure better hygiene and health standards. It called for specific protocols to manage COVID-19 in existing facilities, including proper isolation measures and enhanced medical support. The report also advocated for immediate actions to provide adequate housing for the homeless and those in informal settlements, ensuring access to basic sanitary and healthcare facilities.

Social workers directly working with asylum seekers expressed concern about the fact that the suspension of administrative services for regulating immigration status and interruptions in social services hindered migrants' path to social inclusion. Educational and work experiences, essential for promoting integration, were disrupted during the lockdown, affecting migrants' well-being and future prospects. Furthermore social workers observed a range of emotional responses among migrants, including stress, anxiety, depression, and feelings of abandonment. The uncertainty about the future, job prospects, and social isolation contributed to mental distress and emotional challenges among migrants. Some reported that asylum seekers living in reception centers faced challenges in accessing healthcare services during the crisis. The lack of personal protective equipment and overcrowded living conditions in some centers increased the health risks for asylum seekers and hindered their access to essential medical care (Sanfelici, 2021).

At a local level, on March 20, 2020 group of concerned citizens, advocates, and organizations involved in humanitarian efforts addressed a letter (Fondazione Alexander Langer Stiftung, 2020) to the Provincial Council of South Tyrol, Italy. The primary focus of the letter was to urge the authorities to take immediate and comprehensive action regarding the accommodation of asylum seekers and homeless individuals during the COVID-19 pandemic. It emphasized the necessity of providing immediate accommodation for asylum seekers and homeless individuals to protect them from the risks posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, given the vulnerability of these populations due to their living conditions and lack of access to proper hygiene and healthcare facilities.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The COVID-19 pandemic posed significant challenges for Italy, particularly in managing the needs of asylum seekers within the broader public health crisis. The Italian government and regional authorities implemented a range of measures to protect public health while ensuring the continuity of essential services for asylum seekers. The legal framework established through the Civil Protection Code and emergency decree-laws provided the necessary tools for an agile response, albeit with a notable centralization of power.

Key legislative actions, such as Decree-Law No. 9/2020 and Decree-Law No. 18/2020, played a crucial role in maintaining the legal status of asylum seekers during the pandemic. These laws suspended deadlines

for residence permit applications and extended the validity of existing permits, preventing legal penalties for delays caused by the pandemic. Additionally, the suspension of hearings for asylum applications and the closure of immigration offices highlighted the need for flexible administrative procedures during such crises.

The report underscores the importance of maintaining accommodation and providing health safeguards for asylum seekers. The Italian government's decision to keep asylum seekers in existing reception facilities, even when legal conditions for their stay had expired, trying to ensure stability and continuity. Strict health monitoring protocols, including preliminary medical examinations and mandatory quarantines, were essential in preventing COVID-19 outbreaks within these communities.

Local measures in the Province of Bolzano and the Municipality of Bolzano further illustrate the tailored responses to the pandemic. Enhanced hygiene practices, regular health monitoring, and specific accommodations for symptomatic individuals were critical components of these local strategies. The involvement of social services and collaboration with various associations ensured support for asylum seekers and homeless individuals during the crisis.

Despite these efforts, the report identifies significant challenges, particularly regarding overcrowded conditions in large collective centers and inadequate healthcare access. These issues highlight the need for systemic reforms to ensure better health and hygiene standards in accommodation facilities. The call for a decentralized accommodation system and enhanced medical support is crucial for protecting vulnerable populations during public health emergencies.

Moreover, the pandemic's impact on the mental health and well-being of asylum seekers cannot be overlooked. The suspension of administrative services, social isolation, and disruptions in education and work opportunities contributed to psychological distress among asylum seekers. Addressing these mental health challenges requires a coordinated effort to provide adequate support and ensure the social inclusion of migrants.

In conclusion, the Italian response to COVID-19 demonstrates the complexities of managing a public health crisis while upholding the rights and needs of asylum seekers. The lessons learned from this period underscore the importance of flexible legal frameworks, comprehensive health protocols, and coordinated support systems. By addressing the identified gaps and implementing the recommended reforms, Italy and the Autonomous Province of Bolzano can better safeguard the health and rights of asylum seekers in future emergencies.

REFERENCES

- Alber, E. (2020) *Action and reaction: What Covid-19 can teach us about Italian regionalism*, Eureka! Science Blogs [Online]. Available at <https://www.eurac.edu/doi/10-57708-b6604110> (Accessed 26 June 2024).
- Alber, E. and Zgaga, T. (2021) 'Ein Jahr Pandemiemanagement in Italien und Südtirol. Durchregieren auf Sicht und Südtirols Sonderweg', in Elisabeth Alber, Alice Engl, Günther Pallaver (ed) *Politika 21: Südtiroler Jahrbuch für Politik, Annuario di politica dell'Alto Adige, Anuar de politica di Südtirol* [Online], politika – Südtiroler Gesellschaft für Politikwissenschaft, 43–69. Available at <https://politika.autonomyexperience.org/21/ein-jahr-pandemiemanagement-in-italien-und-suedtirol> (Accessed 8 March 2024).
- Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione (2020) 'Emergenza Covid-19: L'impatto sui diritti delle/dei cittadini/e Stranieri/e e le misure di tutela necessarie: una prima ricognizione' [Online]. Available at https://www.asgi.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/EMERGENZA-COVID-19_DIRITTI-STRANIERI-22-marzo-finale.pdf (Accessed 12.06.24).
- Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione (ASGI) Emilia Romagna (2020) 'Sui permessi di soggiorno nel periodo di emergenza da Coronavirus' [Online]. Available at <https://www.asgi.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/9.4.2020-ASGI-ER-rinnovo-permessi-ai-tempi-del-coronavirus.pdf> (Accessed 12.06.24).
- Brentari, M. and Recla, S. (2021) *Impatti della gestione dello stato di emergenza per Covid-19 sulla qualità della vita dei cittadini e delle cittadine: Indagine esplorativa nella città di Bolzano*, Comune di Bolzano.
- Fondazione Alexander Langer Stiftung (2020) *Lettera aperta alle istituzioni: Accoglienza senza fissa dimora a Bolzano durante la cd. Emergenza Covid-19* [Online], Fondazione | Alexander Langer | Stiftung. Available at <https://www.alexanderlanger.org/it/948/4551> (Accessed 19 June 2024).
- Gazzetta Ufficiale (31/01/2020) *Delibera del Consiglio dei Ministri 31 gennaio 2020* [Online]. Available at <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2020/02/01/20A00737/sg> (Accessed 17 May 2024).
- Questura di Bolzano (2020) *Avviso per i cittadini* [Online]. Available at <https://questure.poliziadistato.it/it/Bolzano/articolo/18035e6bbdef0c2c389559368> (Accessed 2 July 2024).
- Sanfelici, M. (2021) 'The Impact of the COVID-19 Crisis on Marginal Migrant Populations in Italy', *SAGE Publications, American Behavioral Scientist*, 65(10), pp. 1323–1341.
- Ufficio centrale di statistica (2022) *Richieste Asilo 2020 - Ufficio centrale di statistica* [Online], Ministero dell'Interno. Available at https://ucs.interno.gov.it/ucs/download.php?f=Spages&s=download.php&id_sito=1263&file=L0ZJTEVTL0FsbGVnYXRpUGFnLzEyNjMvSU5UMDAwMjktUkIDSEIFU1RFX0FTSUxPX0RBVElFMjAyMC54bHN4&&coming=Y29udGVudXRpL0RhdGlfcmlvVsYXRpdmlfYWlfcmljaGlzGVudGlFYXNpbG9faW50XzAwMDI5LTc3NDQ3NTYuaHRt (Accessed 2 July 2024).